

USING DIDACTIC GAMES TO DEVELOP MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATIONS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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“There is no, and cannot be, full-fledged mental development without play. The game is a huge bright window through which a life-giving stream of ideas and concepts pours into the spiritual world of the child. The game is a spark that ignites the flame of inquisitiveness and curiosity

V.A. Sukhomlinsky

Relevance. Mathematics plays a huge role in mental education and in the development of intelligence. Its study contributes to the development of memory, speech, imagination, emotions; forms perseverance, patience, creative potential of the individual. The main purpose of doing mathematics is to give the child a sense of self-confidence, based on the fact that the world is ordered and therefore comprehensible, and therefore predictable for a person. Teaching mathematics to preschool children is unthinkable without the use of didactic games. Their use well helps the perception of the material and therefore the child takes an active part in the cognitive process.

Didactic game requires perseverance, a serious attitude, the use of the thought process. Play is a natural way for a child to develop.

In the course of games and exercises with entertaining mathematical material, children master the ability to search for solutions on their own.

Purpose: creation of conditions for the development of elementary mathematical concepts in preschool children through didactic games.

Tasks:

- analyze the psychological and pedagogical literature on this topic.
- make a selection of didactic games, tasks;
- use the developed material in mathematics classes with preschool children;
- actively influence the comprehensive development of children:

enrich with new ideas and concepts; consolidate knowledge; activate mental activity (the ability to compare, generalize, classify, analyze).

Expected Result:

- activation of the cognitive interest of preschoolers;
 - development of attention, memory, speech, imagination, logical thinking;
- formation of elementary mathematical representations.

All didactic games can be divided into three types: games with objects, board games and word games.

In games with objects, children learn to compare, establish similarities and differences between objects. The value of these games is that with their help children get acquainted with the signs of objects: color, size, shape.

Word games are built on the words and actions of the players. In such games, children learn about the world around them, deepen their acquired knowledge in new connections, in new circumstances, they are also aimed at developing speech and correct orientation in space.

Board-printed games are diverse in types: paired pictures, lotto, dominoes, mosaics, split pictures and cubes. The task of this type of game is to teach children logical thinking, to develop their ability to make up a whole object from separate parts, to establish similarities and differences between objects, to teach them to compare and highlight the features of objects.

Also, when forming elementary mathematical abilities in preschoolers, you can use games for planar modeling, puzzle games, and joke tasks.

But, despite the variety of games, their main task should be the development of logical thinking, namely the ability to establish the simplest patterns: the order of alternation of figures in color, shape, size.

Stages of work.

1. The study of literature on the topic.

During the year, study the necessary methodological literature, as well as journal articles, familiarize yourself with materials from Internet sources.

1.	Z.A. Mikhailova "Game entertaining tasks for preschoolers", M.: Education 1990.
2.	Practical course of mathematics for preschoolers. Guidelines. — M.: Balass, 2003 — 256 p.
3.	T. A. Falkovich, L. P. Barylkina "Formation of mathematical representations": Classes for preschoolers in institutions of additional education. — M.: VAKO, 2005 — 208 p.
4.	"Subject - didactic games with mathematical content" - A. A. Smolentseva.
5.	L. G. Peterson, N. P. Kholina "Player". Practical course of mathematics for preschoolers. Guidelines. - M. : Balass, 2003 - 256 p.
6.	Smolentseva A. A., Suvorova O. V. Mathematics in problem situations for young children. SPb. : Detstvo-press, 2004.
7.	Magazines "Preschool education", "Child in kindergarten", "Kindergarten. Everything for the teacher.

2. Drawing up a card file of didactic games on mathematical development for preschool children (during the year).

3. Creation of a subject-developing environment in a group (corner of cognitive development).

4. Working with children.

Timing	The content of the work	Use of d/games
September	Monitoring of initial knowledge about elementary mathematical representations.	Didactic games for mastering the concept of "color": "Let's make beads for a doll", "Colored water", "Colored sticks".

October	Formation of ideas about the properties of objects in the immediate environment: color, shape, size. Isolation of signs of difference and similarity.	Didactic games for the development of ideas about quantities: "Decorate the rug", "Houses for cubs", "Let's treat the mice with tea", "Colored cubes".
november	Combining objects into a group by color, shape, size.	"Find a pair", "Spread into boxes."
December	Selection of a part of a group. Finding "extra" items.	e / game "What is superfluous?", "What has changed?"
January	Acquaintance with the concepts of "one", "many".	Didactic games for the development of quantitative ideas: "Into the forest for mushrooms", "Raspberries for cubs", "Treat bunnies".
February	Comparison of groups of objects by quantity (<i>the same, more, less</i>).	Didactic games for the development of equality based on a comparison of two groups of objects: "Let's treat squirrels with mushrooms", "Bugs on leaves", "Butterflies and flowers".

March	Acquaintance with a visual representation of numbers 1-3, the formation of the ability to correlate a number with a quantity. Formation of ideas about the direct comparison of objects in length and width (<i>longer - shorter, wider - narrower, higher - lower</i>).	Didactic games: "Pick the paths to the houses", "Fix the rug", "Bridges for rabbits", "Pick the paths to the houses".
April	Acquaintance with geometric shapes: circle and ball, square and cube, triangle, rectangle, oval. Acquaintance with a visual representation of numbers 4-5, the formation of the ability to correlate a number with a quantity.	Didactic games: "Geometric Lotto", "Spread the figures into houses", "Rolling - not rolling", "Find a pair in shape."
May	Formation of spatial representations: on-above-under, left-right, top-bottom, outside-inside, behind-front, etc. Quantitative and ordinal counting from 1 to 5. Comparison of the previous and subsequent numbers.	Didactic games for location in space: "Take a toy", "Toy store". Didactic games for the ability to correlate numbers with quantity: "Pathfinders", "Builders", "Toy Store".

5. Work with parents and caregivers.

1. Participation of parents in the production of didactic games and demonstration material.	During a year
2. Conducting individual consultations and conversations.	During a year
3. Consultation on the topic: "Didactic games for teaching mathematics to preschoolers" (for educators)	October

4. Conducting a consultation for parents on the topic "The role of didactic games in the education of preschool children."	November
5. Consultation "Teaching preschoolers mathematics in a family."	December
6. Formation of mathematical abilities in preschoolers. Ways and forms of work. (caregivers)	January
7. Individual consultation on the topic: "Orientation in space relative to the subject"	February
8. Folder-slider "Mathematics in the life of a child"	March
9. Recommendations: "We form spatial representations" 10. "How to teach children to determine the properties of objects."	April

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